

SOLVING TYPICAL LOGISTICS TASKS USING THE STAMM APPLICATION

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Abstract

The features of solving logistical problems using modern computer modeling tools are considered. The use of specialized software allows you to obtain the results of optimization or risk assessment in logistics management in the shortest possible time. The paper analyzes various application software packages designed for this purpose. The problems of developing logistics models are considered, a methodology for solving logistics problems in the Stamm 4.3 system based on an object-oriented approach, UML modeling and tabular simulation is presented.

Keywords: simulation modeling, logistics, optimization of inventory management, object-oriented approach, UML modeling

Introduction

The use of computer modeling in solving logistics optimization problems involves some features [3, 4, 8, 12]:

1. Automation of the decision-making process. Computer modeling allows you to quickly create and analyze various scenarios, which simplifies the decision-making process.

2. Taking into account a large number of factors. Logistics systems can be very complex and include many factors, such as delivery time, cost of transportation, cargo volume, etc. Computer modeling allows you to take into account all these factors and optimize the operation of the system as a whole.

3. The possibility of conducting experiments. With the help of computer modeling, experiments can be carried out and various hypotheses can be tested, which makes it possible to improve the operation of the logistics system.

4. More accurate data analysis. Computer modeling allows for more accurate data analysis and identification of hidden patterns, which can lead to more effective optimization of the logistics system.

5. Risk reduction. Computer modeling allows you to predict possible problems and risks associated with the logistics system, which allows you to take measures to minimize them.

There is a significant amount of software that can be used to solve logistical problems. We note among the most famous, highlighting the features:

1. Excel is one of the most popular tools for this purpose. It allows you to create tables, graphs and charts, as well as perform data analysis and optimization.

2. MATLAB is a powerful tool for solving mathematical problems, including logistical ones. It provides a wide range of functions and tools for data analysis, modeling, and optimization.

3. GAMS (General Algebraic Modeling System) is a software that is used to model and optimize logistics systems. It allows you to create and solve complex mathematical models using a special modeling language.

4. Llamasoft is a software that is used to optimize logistics systems and supply chain management. It allows data analysis, modeling and optimization, as well as provides tools for risk management and decision-making.

5. Simul8 is a software that is used to model and optimize business processes and logistics systems. It allows you to create simulation models, analyze data, and optimize.

6. AnyLogic is a simulation environment used for modeling and optimizing complex systems, including logistics. It provides a wide range of tools for modeling, analysis and optimization, and also allows you to use various modeling methods, including system dynamics, agent-based modeling and discrete event modeling.

In addition, there are many software products that solve a strictly limited list of tasks [2, 7, 13].

According to XJ Technologies (the manufacturer of the Anylogic package mentioned above), it is the simulation models implemented for the field of logistics that are in the greatest demand today [1].

The software packages discussed above solve the identified problems to one degree or another in computer modeling of logistical tasks, while having certain disadvantages. For example, all of the above are commercial products with a decent price [9].

Object and methods of research

The object of research in this paper is typical logistic tasks. The non-commercial product Stamm 4.3 is used to solve them.

Visual design of models

This application has been developed and improved by the author for more than 20 years, and if the system was originally intended to organize the simplest simulation using spreadsheets, a number of functions are currently available that allow you to solve a variety of tasks [5, 6, 10, 11, 14].

As an example, let's consider the simplest inventory optimization task implemented using Excel. This model takes into account the single-period inventory management model. It is necessary to determine the size of the ordered batch of Part for some future period of time, if it is known that demand D is a random variable with a normal distribution law (the average value is M_s , the mean square deviation is S_s). In the event that

the demand is less than the batch that was ordered, the costs will amount to

$$C = Ch \cdot (Part - D)$$

where Ch - the cost of storing a unit of goods.

If the ordered lot is not enough to meet the demand, then the costs will include the costs of the deficit

$$C = Cd \cdot (D - Part),$$

where Cd - penalty for shortage of a unit of goods.

The problem is solved by repeatedly replaying the situation in the warehouse, taking into account the given law of demand distribution. In the case of using Excel, pseudo-simulation takes place, since demand variation is carried out as a result of changing related cells in adjacent rows, and model parameters such as the initial stock level and production volume are entered into the model manually (Fig. 1). This is due to Excel's limitations on the use of cross-references.

Fig. 1. Simulation of a single-period replenishment system. Excel

In case of a need for a multistep Monte Carlo, it is not very convenient to use such a model. The same task is solved much easier in Stamm and looks more compact (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Simulation of a single-period replenishment system. Stamm 4.3

At the same time, you can observe the system change in a separate window, adding the variables necessary for monitoring there (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Parameter control window for tabular simulation. Stamm 4.3

However, it is most convenient to solve optimization problems of logistics using the full potential of the system under consideration. There are a number of diverse tasks for optimizing logistics systems, nevertheless having similar elements.

The enlarged simulation algorithm using cells in the table provides the following actions (Fig. 4). Initialization of virtual model time variables – initial value (T_0), final value (T_{max}) and modeling step (ΔT).

Рис. 4. Основной алгоритм табличной имитации. Stamm 4.3

Before the expiration of the model time, a cycle is performed, at each step of which the current state of the system is determined, including, if necessary, a nested cycle inside the main cycle of the model that processes the state of a finite number of similar virtual objects. Such objects, in accordance with the principles of object-oriented modeling, have the same structure, a set of variable parameters, and connections with other components of the model.

In the case of solving a large range of tasks in the field of logistics in transport, it is possible to allocate objects of the "Resource Consumer" class. Instances of this class can be, for example, cars that consume fuel, tires, etc. during operation. This consumption Y is a function of external and other factors (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n) and time. In turn, this class has two fundamentally different derived classes that continuously consume a re-

source over time and consume it discretely. The peculiarities of the latter include a change in its state in the process of resource consumption. Examples of the second subclass are cars that periodically undergo scheduled maintenance and need to replace some parts, oil,

etc. Figure 5 shows an algorithm for processing objects of this class in a tabular simulation. This algorithm, like the class itself, is abstract. Its specific implementation will depend on the characteristics of the object being modeled.

Fig. 5. Template of the algorithm "Resource consumer object" in the Stamm 4.3 program

Results

In the process of simulation of logistical tasks involving a large number of similar objects as components of the model, such as cars, in order to save PC memory, it is impractical to use copies of each of them during the entire life of the model. The spreadsheet-based simulation model considered in this paper pro-

vides for processing all objects at each step of the simulation with reading the current state from the database and further saving changes (Fig. 4, 5).

Using the considered approaches, several simulation models have been developed in the Stamm system. For example, a model for optimizing the stocks of pneumatic cylinders of buses (Fig. 6).

Simulation of air suspension buses failures.swb										
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Current	day	1	Temperature	-13.67		Intensity	On the line	Error!	
2		month	1	Precipitation	0.86		0.0185239	Reserve	1	
3	Days from the beginning		6							
4	Number of buses	98		Pneumoballons						
5	Bus number	Initial status	Mileage	1	2	3	4			
6	7	0	200.92879	0.999205064	0.8889829	0.0044407	0.0030372	80775.306		
7				75357.94591	69629.042	704.34176	66403.803			
8				0.013284488	0.0078160	0.0091708	0.8762813	Repair	Status after the ru	Waiting
9				6	70555.982	76518.259	70301.087	0	0	0
10	Expenses			Current			Refusals			
11	Simple 1 bus per day	9600	Under repair	60	180000	In stock	200		Maximum level	200
12	The cost of a pneumatic	15000	Waiting	0	0	Order	0	0	Minimum level	180
13	Replacement	3000		For storage	2883673.4				Term of execution	90
14	Storage of 1 pneumatic c	150		Order	0				Ordered	0
15	Ordering 1 cylinder	1000		Total	3063673.4					

Fig. 6. The model for optimizing the stocks of pneumatic cylinders in the Stamm 4.3 program

The state of the air suspension of buses is reproduced in cells A6..J9. Data on the current state of the bus is modeled using special controller cells (Fig. 7).

The scan controller ? X

Scanning Sheet ...

Set name active books and column from data will be copying, for example Sheet 1!D

Scanning every units, the model time

By conditions

Set conditions selection data, for example Cells columns A and B scanning Sheet? must be equal to cells D5 C7 current one (A=D5 and B=C7)

Save back

Taking into account

Fig. 7. Controller cell for data exchange with the "Buses" table

The contents of the "Buses" table change for each bus when the model time changes (Fig. 8). Factors affecting the resource consumption of pneumatic cylinders are contained in cells E1, E2, G2 of the table containing the simulation model "Stock optimisation" (Fig. 6), they in turn depend on the ambient temperature and others the operating conditions presented in tabular form, the "Weather" sheet (Fig.9).

Simulation of air suspension buses failures.swb										
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	1	6493.292485	4617.904036	1863.267245	74494.65368	10465.26851	68360.03010	75832.60721	2100.58857	0.097417788
2	2	76475.25484	76003.35519	73692.32567	3451.349192	9229.160652	8283.493186	4145.04208	67661.84854	0.966755262
3	3	5112.429271	3064.428494	77391.25716	69586.15618	4192.627909	76477.99637	6026.281955	76477.99637	0.071115785
4	4	73675.53813	231.019163	666.78761	72961.34955	70883.69322	5684.270259	67677.50717	0	0.938405406
5	5	8073.341745	75211.23464	75669.46655	73558.38972	1866.477539	76127.10105	73325.07715	78703.99250	0.121457335
6	6	77084.87629	5051.135174	1582.475005	2255.023158	1365.890057	5758.637037	2255.023158	77084.87629	0.972767826
7	7	75357.94591	69629.04215	704.341766	66403.80351	73509.12930	70555.98212	76769.75173	75357.94591	0.972049520
8	8	75346.72145	73960.90578	2944.143825	77011.30397	68183.14438	6157.344532	76518.25982	8685.074754	0.973155264
9	9	6650.155863	3028.96286	1412.195131	3486.46304	75157.43328	8282.865919	923.709738	70301.08737	0.098361363
10	10	75034.45921	1168.400369	74356.29856	3641.686899	5531.219582	8126.206053	69279.42397	75486.41915	0.999205064

Fig. 8. A sheet with up-to-date data on the status of buses

	A	B	C	D	E
1	1	-18.02	0.98	1.01	
2	2	-23.3	0.7	2.01	
3	3	-27.14	0.86	3.01	
4	4	-21.63	0.37	4.01	
5	5	-20.26	0.74	5.01	
6	6	-13.67	0.33	6.01	
7	7	-26.57	0.43	7.01	
8	8	-24.68	0.32	8.01	
9	9	-27.94	0.06	9.01	
10	10	-29.11	0.89	10.01	

Fig. 9. A sheet with forecast data on the weather and the intensity of operation of "Weather"

Using similar algorithms, logistics management models have also been developed for the repair and maintenance of the Utair helicopter fleet in the North of the Tyumen Region (Fig. 10) and a number of others.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Initial	01/01/2017	152.3030303	Flight experience			Flight experience norms		
2	Final	01/12/2021	Surgut	50	52	Engine TV2-117	Gearbox VR-8	Main rotor bushing	
3	Current	02/06/2017	Noyabrsk	45	48	1500	1500	2000	
4	Month	1	Tazovsky	85	69				
5			Novy Urengoy	100	100		The probability of exten		0.957477
6	Number of aircraft	11							
7				Units					
8	№ aircraft	Basing	Total flying time	Engine TV2-117	Gearbox VR-8	Main rotor bu	Status		
9	3	Surgut	19787	0	970	1381	9		
10				2000	1500				
11			Replace						
12		Engine TV2-117	Gearbox VR-8	Main rotor bushing			Engine TV2-117	Gearbox VR-8	Main rotor bushing
13	Surgut	1	0	0		Surgut	1		1
14	Noyabrsk	0	0	1		Noyabrsk			
15	Tazovsky	0	0	0		Tazovsky			
16	Novy Urengoy	0	0	1		Novy Urengo			
17	Total	0	2	1		Total		Idle 1 aircraft per day	9600

Fig. 10. Tabular simulation model "Logistics management of the main units to the helicopter bases"

Conclusions

The proposed methods of organizing tabular simulation models will reduce the time for their development, as well as use the database of the current state of objects during the simulation experiment for additional analysis and decision-making, both during the simulation and at its completion. The results can be easily transferred from Stamm worksheets to other applications, such as Excel.

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